

Russian Bear with Balalaika Playing Battle Hymns for the Baltics: The Russian Compatriot Policy in the Baltics

Öncel Sençerman¹

Abstract

The compatriot concept is what Russia created and transformed into the compatriot policy in the 1990s. Russia has benefitted from the compatriots abroad as an efficient tool for Russian foreign policy making. Russia has invested in soft power instruments like state organizations since 2003 to influence the Russians and Russian speaking people in the post-Soviet countries, especially in the Baltics. Russia's aggressions in Georgia and Ukraine resulted in a transformation of its soft power policies into a hybrid warfare in the Baltics. This study aims to explain the factors behind this transformation using case study analysis as a method.

Keywords

Russian diaspora; compatriot policy; Baltics; Russian world; soft power

¹ Öncel Sençerman (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3701-2040>) is working as an Assistant Professor at the Department of International Relations at the Faculty of Political Sciences in Aydın Adnan Menderes University in Türkiye. He holds a BA from the prestigious Boğaziçi University in Türkiye. His works mostly focus on negotiation theory, and conflict and peace studies related to Sub-Saharan Africa and the Baltics. E-mail: osencerman@adu.edu.tr.

Introduction

The collapse of the Soviet Union left thousands of ethnic Russians and Russian speaking communities out of the motherland, Russia. The rising nationalism in the Baltics at the end of the 1980s was one of the factors bringing an immediate end to the Soviet Union. The Baltic states, Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania, were the first republics to declare independence. They actually restored their independence. The Baltic states were under Soviet occupation since the Second World War (WWII). The newly independent Baltic states confronted with several problems. One of the vital problems was the Russian-speaking community including the ethnic Russians that constituted almost one third of the total populations of Estonia and Latvia. For the Baltic states it was a 'citizenship' problem, but for Russia it was a 'compatriot' problem since Russia had compatriots in the post-Soviet regions. What Russia wanted was to protect these compatriots' rights at the beginning, so the newly created 'Near Abroad' Policy helped to prepare the legal basis for it. Russia created the concept of compatriots under Yeltsin in the 1990s and improved it under Putin between 2002 and 2014, thanks to several state institutions, as part of soft power strategies benefitting from public diplomacy elements like language, culture, history and religion to influence the compatriots.

Despite the fact that the Color revolutions in Georgia and Ukraine between 2003 and 2005 contributed to the importance of 'soft power' in Russia, actually the Georgian War in 2008 and the Annexation of Crimea in 2014, together with the recent Ukrainian War started in 2022, made Russia distance itself from soft power policies and get closer to hybrid warfare methods like propaganda, disinformation, and cyberattacks. The main research question of this study focuses on the factors causing this transformation of Russian compatriot policy into a hybrid warfare in the Baltics.

The hypothesis of the study is as follows: when soft power policies confront with local reactions and failure in the end, the implementing country can apply hybrid warfare methods to maintain its influence in a country for its vital interests. The Russian compatriot policy that was helping the compatriots abroad with the help of soft power strategies turned into a hybrid warfare with the increasing Russian disinformation campaigns in the Baltics: the Russian bear with balalaika now plays battle hymns for the Baltics during the new Russian hybrid warfare, instead of songs warming the hearts. The study uses case study analysis method as a research methodology and benefits from the literature on Russian diaspora, Russian compatriots abroad, the Baltic states and also from governmental sources. This study contributes to the literature on Baltic studies dealing with the topics like Russian diaspora, Baltic region's security, Russian hybrid warfare in the Baltic states.

This study consists of two main parts. The first part tries to explain the concept of compatriot and the evolution of compatriot policy in Russia, and the second part is about how Russia has been using its compatriot policy in the Baltics in recent years and what are the factors of a transformation into a hybrid warfare.

The concept of 'compatriot' and the compatriot policy

The Russians and Russian-speaking communities that stayed within the post-Soviet countries following the disintegration of the Soviet Union were one of the important issues of the Russian Federation. Russia stepped up to protect these communities and their rights, especially from a humanitarian perspective and with respect to citizenship issues, without losing time under Yeltsin's presidency. Starting from 1994, following the introduction of the term 'compatriots' by the President Yeltsin and Minister of Foreign Affairs Kozyrev in 1992, the concept has been transformed into a "concrete state policy" that could be followed on the laws and schedules of the Russian state with reflections in foreign

policy making processes (Zevelev, 2016). Zevelev (2016) also asserts that the concept of 'compatriot' and 'Russian World' later developed into political terms constituting a "nationalist narrative about the necessity of Russia's revival as a great power and its revanche in the post-Soviet space".

The first policies to politically benefit from the Russian diaspora started to emerge under Yeltsin with the famous 'Yeltsin Doctrine' also known as 'Russian Monroe Doctrine' for the 'Near Abroad', which was based on the Russian Foreign Policy Concept of 1992 (Coolican, 2021: 8; Laruell, 2015: 9). What Yeltsin obtained with the 'Near Abroad Doctrine' also helped Russia to further its public diplomacy policies in the former Soviet zones. Owing to the ideas of the Foreign Minister Kozyrev and Karaganov, the former chairman of the Council for Foreign and Defense Policy, in the beginning of the 1990s, the 'compatriots' who found themselves in the Near Abroad following the disintegration of the Soviet Union turned into an important tool for Russian foreign policy, which is also known in the literature as 'Karaganov Doctrine' (Maliukevicius, 2013: 79).

In addition to the first legal actions taken to protect the compatriots, Article 61 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation adopted in 1993 guarantees the protection and guardianship of its citizens abroad (Constitution of the Russian Federation, 1993). Article 7 of the Russian Federal Law Numbered 62-FZ dated 31 May 2002 on Citizenship of Russian Federation is again about the 'Protection of and Assistance to Citizens of Russian Federation Outside the Russian Federation' underlining that the citizens outside the Federation shall be provided with protection and assistance, and the state authorities, diplomatic missions, consular services outside the Russian Federation shall ensure those citizens enjoy all the rights stated in the Constitution and federal laws (Refworld, 2002).

This Federal Law symbolizes the importance given to the compatriot policy in the early Putin era by underlying the protection and assistance to the compatriots, which would later work in the Georgian War in 2008, the Annexation of Crimea in 2014, and the Ukrainian War in 2022 as an excuse for the protection of the Russian citizens. Putin's presidency brought along new institutions for the compatriots following this Federal Law. Important state institutions to implement soft power strategies toward the Russian compatriots were mostly created by presidential decrees starting from 2003. The first one is the World Congress of Compatriots that brings together the compatriots every three years in Russia and the other two significant ones are the Russkiy Mir Foundation and the Rossotrudnichestvo that were established in 2007 and 2008, respectively. Together with these state institutions, the Russian Orthodox Church also became an important player for the soft power strategies of Moscow to influence the Russian compatriots abroad.

The World Congress of Compatriots is one of the big events Russia organizes every three years since 2003 regarding the core topics of the compatriot policy such as minority rights, repatriation programs, and cultural and linguistic aspects. It welcomes compatriot representatives coming from the post-Soviet states to meet the Russian president and other high officials of the Russian state (Grigas, 2016, p. 40). During the 7th World Congress of Compatriots Living Abroad in 2021, Russian Foreign Minister Lavrov stated that crafty methods were used to discriminate against the Russian compatriots for their Russian language and culture, and stressed that Russian language has been excluded from public use in the Baltic countries. Lavrov also mentioned in his speech that Russian media agencies run by the compatriots have been contributing to reinforcing Russian World's identity and enlarging its Russian-speaking zone (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation, 2021). The latest Congress and the speech addressed by Lavrov show how Russia is concerned about the Baltic states and the compatriots living there.

Russkiy Mir Foundation was established in 2007 by a decree of the Russian President Putin. The Foundation aims at "promoting Russian language, as Russia's national heritage and a significant

aspect of Russian and world culture, and supporting Russian language teaching programs abroad” (Russkiy Mir Foundation). The Foundation is a joint body of the ministries of Foreign Affairs and Education. It creates intercultural projects for developing Russian Centers in collaboration with educational organizations in the world, aiming to promote the Russian language. It also offers grants for projects focusing on the Russian language and on cultural-humanitarian issues (Russkiy Mir Foundation). The Russkiy Mir Foundation was actually an attempt to rethink the significance of public and cultural diplomacy for Russian foreign policy, especially following the color revolutions in Georgia in 2003 and in Ukraine in 2004 (Koval et al, 2022). Maliukevicius sets forth that these socio-political events in Georgia and Ukraine made Russia consider ‘soft power’ more seriously (2013: 74). Apart from promoting Russian language, the task list of the Foundation also includes promoting information on the compatriots, supporting the compatriots’ activities and the media in Russian language, and also cooperating with the Russian Orthodox Church (ROC) (Koval et al, 2022). For this reason, Kallas asserts that Russkiy Mir Foundation is associated with “three types of identification with Russia: cultural (Russian language, Orthodox faith, historical memory), political (Russian state) and economic (being an economic actor in favor of Russia)” (2016, p. 8).

Only one year later after the Russkiy Mir Foundation was created, the ‘Rossotrudnichestvo’ was established, in 2008, by the decree of the Russian President with the name of ‘the Federal Agency for the Commonwealth of Independents States, Compatriots Living Abroad, and International Humanitarian Cooperation’. The Federal Agency actually is a continuation of a former Soviet institution founded in 1925 under the name of All-Union Society for Cultural Communication Abroad (VOX) and renamed in 1958 as the Union of Soviet Societies of Friendship and Cultural Ties with Foreign Countries, then transformed into Roszarubezhcenter in 1994 (Rossotrudnichestvo). The Rossotrudnichestvo, whose mission, as stated on its official webpage, is “to strengthen Russia’s humanitarian influence in the world” is also known as “Russian House” and it is represented by 73 centers in 62 different countries around the world. The Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) constitutes the main priority of its activities such as cooperation and participation into assistance programs. The Baltic states do not host any Russian Houses. The internet page of the Rossotrudnichestvo offers information for the compatriots regarding the support given to cultural and humanitarian initiatives, resettlement to the motherland and how they can protect their rights in case of facing any violation of rights and “manifestation of Russophobia’ (Rossotrudnichestvo). Its main tasks include providing objective pictures of modern Russia, cooperation in the field of humanitarian activities, including festivals and cultural events, promoting the Russian language and organizing cultural, scientific, and educational exchange programs, cooperating with the Russian compatriots and finally offering international aid for development (Panova, 2015: 90).

Beside the Rossotrudnichestvo, there is one more state organization that actively works in the field of compatriots: the Alexander Gorchakov Public Diplomacy Fund. This organization was established through a presidential decree in 2010, with a main mission of encouraging the progress of public diplomacy and supporting the establishment of Russian-friendly public, business and political environments (The Gorchakov Fund). These state-founded-and-funded organizations are instruments for implementing Russia’s soft power strategies, yet almost all of them focus mainly on promoting Russian language and culture aiming the compatriots abroad. One of the drawbacks of Russia’s soft power is that the agencies active in public diplomacy are mostly state organizations that only welcome officially recognized NGOs and there is no clear distinction between the two important soft power agencies, Russkiy Mir Foundation and the Rossotrudnichestvo, which, given their complex activities, is a source of confusion for other countries (Sergunin, 2014, p. 177).

The Russian Orthodox Church (ROC) has had an important impact on Russian political, cultural, and social life even during the Soviet times. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, the Russian leaders strengthened the church to become “the carrier of moral and conservative values” (Merilo, 2024). The ROC plays an important role in Russia’s soft power activities. The Patriarch Kirill of the ROC has been allegedly supporting Putin’s foreign policies including the compatriot policy, and Grigas (2016: 32) asserts that the increasing influence of the ROC in Russia and in international arena might be associated with the revitalization of the church since the collapse of the Soviet Union.

Apart from these state organizations and the ROC, the statements of Russian leaders like Putin and Medvedev supported the Russian compatriot policies focusing on soft power usage especially in the former Soviet territories. Following the Georgian War, in August 2008, during the interview with the Russian television channels, President Medvedev emphasized that protecting the lives and dignity of Russian citizens no matter where they were was among the indisputable priorities of the Russian Federation. Medvedev also stated there were some regions where Russia had ‘privileged interests’ like the regions where Russia had ‘special historical relations’ and friendly relationships (President of Russia, 2008). Putin addressed the participants at the Valdai International Discussion Club on 24 October 2014 in Sochi underlining the importance of the role of humanitarian factors like education, science, healthcare, and culture and emphasizing that the soft power stemming from these sources would rely on the success in human capital rather than propaganda (President of Russia, 2014).

Grigas (2016: 4) interprets these soft power strategies of Russia regarding the compatriots as “neo-imperial policies” that have important roots in Russian history dating back to the Tsarist Russia and urges that “there is an undeniable historical continuity between present Russian imperial projects and past projects of the Romanovs and the Soviets”. Russia’s compatriot policies are playing an important role for the current regime in terms of looking for territorial advantages in the ex-Soviet states, especially if three conditions are being met: “(1) a large and concentrated population of Russian speakers or ethnic Russians; (2) that population resides in territories bordering Russia; (3) the population is receptive to Russia’s influence”. Grigas (2016: 61) also argues there is a steady path in Russian policies related with the former Soviet zones and the society living there, especially covering the compatriots. He labels it as “the Russian reimperialization policy trajectory”, that consists of seven steps: “(1) soft power, (2) humanitarian policies, (3) compatriot policies, (4) information warfare, (5) passportization, (6) protection, and finally (7) annexation” (2016: 10). Russia benefits from the rhetoric of ‘human rights’ by raising issues related with human rights and using them to assist and protect the compatriots. Russia has also allegedly been using the compatriots for achieving geopolitical control in former Soviet regions by using soft power (Grigas, 2016: 34). However, as mentioned above, soft power usage by Russia changed its trajectory to what we can call a hybrid warfare especially after the Annexation of Crimea in 2014 including information war to influence the compatriots abroad, especially in the Baltics. The next part of the article is aiming to display this transformation.

Compatriots in the Baltics and Russian hybrid warfare

The Russians came to the Baltics and established Tartu around 11th century and became the majority of the population of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania between 13th and 15th centuries even long before the Old Believers came to the Baltics in 17th century following the split of the Russian Church (Simonyan, 2022: 147). The Baltics region turned into the territory of the Russian Empire in the 18th century following the Great Northern War and only after a short break in 20th century, it became a part of the Soviet Union for about 50 years, which resulted in an increase of the Russian immigrants and settlers in the region. When the Baltic states restored their independence in 1991 there were

already several different Russian speaking groups: those who had lived there even before the Bolshevik Revolution and the WWII, including the Old Believers; the Russian intelligentsia that came after the WWII from Moscow and St. Petersburg; the employees like doctors, engineers, teachers, skilled workers, technicians of post-war industrialization; soldiers; and finally the “last minute migrants who were the least educated” (Simonyan, 2022: 149). Thompson (2019) asserts that since the early 1940s until the beginning of the 1990, the Baltic states were subjected to “Russian gaslighting designed to make people doubt their national history, culture, and economic development” and for this reason, the Soviets distorted the history by rewriting it and made manipulations of the economic data to show that the Baltic states’ economies were boosting under the Soviet regime. This strategy used by the Russians did not vanish, even after the collapse of the Union and the independence of the Baltic states, and Russia went on disinformation campaigns in the region by using the Russian language and criticisms over the issue of falsifying history. As a consequence of the collapse of the Soviet Union, as Maliukevicius (2013: 78) asserts, “Russia not only lost the integrating ideology of Communist utopia, but the institutional potential of the Soviet Union’s public diplomacy was slowly degrading as well”.

The collapse of the Soviet Union also uncovered the nationalistic reactions coming from the governments of the former Soviet Baltic Republics, especially from Latvia and Estonia; mostly reactions to the Russians and Russian speakers regarding their citizenship and naturalization issues. After obtaining independence from the Soviet Union, the Latvian Parliament adopted a resolution in 1991 restoring citizenship status for the people who “were interwar citizens and their direct descendants” and between the years of 1992 and 1995 the Citizenship and Migration Department (CID) of Latvia rendered the law in a confining way rejecting Russian speaking people in connection with the departing Soviet Russian army, which created problems in international arena and also between Russia and Latvia (Muznieks, 2006: 15). Even though Latvia passed another law on citizenship in 1994 giving naturalization rights for some groups, it continued to exclude people associated with the KGB officials and Soviet army officers (Muzniek, 2006: 16). Similar to Latvia, following the restoration of independence in 1991, the non-Estonians represented around 40% of the total Estonian population, an important citizenship issue in Estonia. To deal with it, the Estonian government started to issue ‘grey passports’ for the non-citizens, giving them the right to have official residence in Estonia (Hoffmann et al, 2017, p. 153). Different from Latvia and Estonia, Lithuania, after the restoration of independence, passed a law on citizenship that allowed anybody to gain the right of citizenship regardless of their nationality or duration of residence, while its two neighboring countries have three different social groups like “citizens of the countries of residence, citizens of Russia, and aliens or non-citizens” (Simonyan, 2022: 150). The citizenship legislation in Estonia and Latvia created problems with Russia over the issue of ethnic Russians and Russian-speakers regarding human rights. The Russians constitute 23.7% of the population in Estonia, 24.5% in Latvia, and 5% in Lithuania. Russian speakers constitute 28.5% of the population in Estonia, 33.8% in Latvia, and 6.8% in Lithuania today. (The World Factbook). The current Russians and Russian-speaking people in the Baltic countries still continue to be an important issue for the governments of these countries as it makes them open for any possible Russian influence including military and security related concerns.

The Center for Countering Disinformation of Ukraine (2023) asserts that according to the research of several international journalists, Russia has been carrying out a ‘soft power’ strategy for the Baltics states to increase its influence in each Baltic country since 2021. This strategy includes stopping militarization in these countries, curbing the NATO influence, preventing support for opposition against Russia, and sustaining the existence of Russian language in education and within the society by “maintaining a common historical memory and promoting historical symbols of Russia

(Center for Countering Disinformation of Ukraine, 2023). Galeotti (2019) claims that Russia targets more than the Baltic states in the Baltic region and other targets are the EU, NATO, the USA and the Nordic states by using different modes of engagement like deploying troops and Iskander-M missiles in Kaliningrad enclave, military exercises like 'Zapad' and information operations including any methods from espionage and hacking to soft power usage and propaganda war. Like Galeotti, Burduli (2020) urges that Russia is using propaganda as a 'soft power' tool, yet there is a distinction between the classic definition of soft power and what Russia has been doing since Russia is not trying to appeal to "a target audience with its values, level of prosperity, political ideals and enhancement of Russia, rather it focuses on distraction and manipulation and prefers to discredit opposing forces". Burduli (2020) also states that since the Baltic states are NATO members and Russia knows what it means to attack a NATO member country, so it prefers to "attack softly by applying means that his opponents are not prepared to counter".

Laruell (2015) mentions different strategies were followed as part of the Near Abroad policy that formed in 2008, such as energy investments by Russian companies like Gazprom and Lukoil; multilateral organizations like the CIS and the Collective Security Treaty Organization; NGO diplomacy that includes funding Russian friendly activities; Russian culture, media and language promotion; resettlement programs; citizenship and passportization; and military involvement as it happened in 1992 in Moldova, in 2008 in Georgia and in 2014 in Crimea. Laruell (2015: 12) also alleges that the concept of Russian World means the Russian zone of influence covering states that Russia thinks that it has a right to say its opinion on and this influence of Russia ranges from common history discourses to military involvement by using economic surroundings and information wars. Grigas (2014: 15) wrote in 2014 that if the Baltic states would not be able to 'fully integrate' the Russian speakers into their communities and lost the soft power war with Russia then these regions could become targets for Russian influence. As Grigas envisioned in 2014, this study also draws attention to this change: from soft power to hybrid warfare.

Between the years of 2010 and 2011 Russian Mir allegedly funded about eight organizations active in Lithuania: the Green Lantern, the International Culture and Arts Center in Klaipeda, the Russian Culture Center in Vilnius, the Visaginas Technology and Business Vocational Education and Training Center, the international recreational center Lupa in Visaginas, the Association of Teachers of Russian Schools in Lithuania, and the Association of Russian Compatriots. Apart from those organizations, Russian language centers at the Lithuanian University of Educational Sciences and Siauliai University were financed for different projects (Motuzaitė, 2012). The Russian government also supported cultural events and festivals like New Wave Jūrmalina, Club of the Funny and Intensive, and the Week of Fine Humor in Jūrmala, Latvia with the help of an organization that had links with Russia in the Baltic states (Panova, 2015: 95). There are Russian centers in Tallinn in Estonia, in Riga and Daugavpils in Latvia, and also in Vilnius in Lithuania (Panova, 2015: 92). Kojola et al (2015: 186) assert that Russian speaking community in Lithuania have been a target for soft power policies implemented by the NGOs and community-related bodies whose number is more than 80 and most of these events are organized under the control and coordination of the Russkiy Mir Foundation, the Gorchakov Foundation, the Rossotrudnichestvo and the Historical Memory Foundation funded by Russia to continue Russian influence within the region.

Nonetheless, Grigas (2016: 155) alleges that the Russian compatriot policy does not only include cultural and linguistic activities in the Baltics, such as the above-mentioned ones, but it also organizes paramilitary activities for the young compatriots in the Soyuz paramilitary camp. Kurmanaev et al (The New York Times, 2024) point out that Lithuania turned out to be a haven for the Russian

opposition that welcomed Belarussians following the 2020 demonstrations in Minsk, Ukrainians and Russians after the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, resulting in a dramatic increase of Russian speaking population in Lithuania, which is considered by some Lithuanian citizens as a 'threat' as the Russians are not considering Lithuania as their 'homeland'. Lithuania's careful 'humanitarian' visa procedures helped to form a highly educated Russian community in Vilnius, which has mostly well-to-do and politically active members. This new Russian community has political groups like 'Golos' for electoral rights and independent news agency workers producing material for the compatriots on social media and also has a popular Russian singer 'Monetochka' serving to the global Russians. These recent developments in Lithuania regarding the increasing number of Russian speakers also create new question marks regarding the vulnerability of Lithuania before the Russian influence and hybrid warfare.

Not unlike the findings of the scholars mentioned above, local intelligence and security bodies also underlines the change in the compatriot policy of Russia from soft power strategies to using hybrid warfare methods like propaganda and information wars. The Estonian Foreign Intelligence Service warns about the links and relations between the compatriots and compatriot organizations like the Russian World and the Moscow House of Compatriots, and the Russian Intelligence Service for the objective of collecting intelligence and propaganda usages (Estonian Foreign Intelligence Service, 2023). The Latvian State Security Service, the VDD, shares a special place for the Russian information influence in the Annual Report 2023 and mentions that Russia used former compatriots who left Latvia for Russia "to influence the opinion of this part of society about developments in Latvia" and provided support for the activities of the compatriots living in Latvia "with campaigns of information influence to discredit the state of Latvia", yet also emphasized that thanks to the countermeasures by the VDD "the level of activity of so-called individual defenders of the rights of compatriots in Latvia was also low last year" (Latvian State Security Service, 2023). Following the Crimean annexation by Russia in 2014, Latvia's capital city Riga welcomed the headquarters of NATO organization, the Strategic Communications Center of Excellence fighting with Russian influence and reporting disinformation activities of Russia (Thompson, 2019). Lithuanian intelligence service, the State Security Department of Lithuania, the VSD states on its official webpage that in spite of the economic issues in Russia, Russia will go on putting pressure on the neighboring countries so as to minimize the influence of the NATO and EU. The VSA also counts these fields among the coverage of Russian intelligence activities: "Lithuanian domestic policy – processes, trends, election campaigns, political leaders, and their personal features; Lithuanian foreign policy – position in international organizations, bilateral relations, specifics of policy formation; economy and energetics – development and prospects of economy, strategic energy projects, their political support or disagreement by the government and possibilities of discrediting" (State Security Department of Lithuania).

Before the invasion of Ukraine, some scholars were claiming that the Russian influence in the Baltics had been fading owing to the EU integration, NATO presence, energy security cooperation, the media in the Baltics reporting that the political atmosphere in the region had been seriously changed from the start of the new millennium, curbing Russia's control over the compatriots (Bergmane, 2020; Bankauskaite et al., 2020; Panova 2015; Coolican, 2021). Bergmane (2020: 481) asserts that the Baltic states' participation into the EU and the NATO "was a geopolitical loss" for Russia, with a new policy of these states to turn back to their European roots and the Crimean annexation in 2014 paved the way for the deployment of NATO troops in the Baltics, where did not have any NATO or American troops before. According to Bergmane (2020, p. 482), another important factor limiting the Russian impact in the region was the transformation of energy policies of these small states that were heavily

depending on Russian gas for their energy needs by 2014. Coolican (2021: 15) alleges that Russian compatriots in the Baltics are not receptive to the Russian soft power influence owing to their “strong transnational connections, benefited from globalization, and have created a robust infrastructure against Russian influence and sharp power”.

In contrast with the above-mentioned findings, the Russian soft power organizations are involving into “espionage and sabotage” activities in the Baltics despite the fact that there is actually no difference between the soft power institutions around the world like the British Council and the Goethe Institute (Panova, 2015: 89). Milosevich (2021) points out the hybrid warfare that Russia has been waging on the EU and the USA to maintain the survival of the Federation, to assume the great power role again and finally to undermine the NATO and EU enlargement to the east. Despite the lack of any official definition of the Russian government or military regarding the definition or objectives of a hybrid warfare, the hybrid warfare Russia has assertedly been waging on the western states is also darkening the contrast between soft power and hard power (Milosevich, 2021). Milosevich (2021) also draws attention to Russia’s ambition to keep the power balance with the West and mainly the USA with its nuclear arsenal as a great power for maintaining its interests in the post-Soviet region including the Near East and neighboring countries like the Baltic states.

Russia has been directing its disinformation campaigns mostly towards the post-communist countries like the Baltic states and Poland, aiming the Russian speaking populations in these countries (The US Congress, 2018: 101). The US Congress Minority Staff Report (2018, p. 101-102) highlights the objectives behind the Russian operations to gain influence in the region as follows: to have control over the Russian diaspora by splitting local populations regarding ethnicity, to create suspicion among the population against the national governments, to weaken western values and democracy by benefiting from populist and radical strategies, to undermine the alliances of the Baltic states with the NATO and EU and finally to depreciate the culture, history, traditions and accomplishments of the Baltic states. Russia is alleged to use its diplomatic missions to fund local NGOs for their activities towards the compatriots and to handle disinformation operations against the exercises of NATO following the establishment of Enhanced Forward Presence to avert any possible Russian aggression in the Baltics (The US Congress, 2018).

The information war of Russia in the Baltics aims to weaken the NATO, EU and the democratic traditions in the Baltics by exaggerating minority-related issues like discrimination against Russophobes and by using fake-news techniques like the rape incident by the German NATO soldiers. Former Lithuanian president Grybauskaitė considers this “militant illiteracy and aggressive populism” an important threat (The Economist, 2019). The social media and the messages created by the bots have a significant place in the information war of Russia in the Baltics and the NATO Strategic Communications Center of Excellence issued a report mentioning that about 70% of the messages about the NATO in the Baltics were created by Russian language bots (The US Congress, 2018). Following the 2007 cyberattacks owing to the Bronze Soldier demonstrations, Estonia established the Cyber Defense League consisting of volunteer IT specialists (Thompson, 2019). It is also possible to find volunteer bodies formed to fight with the Russian disinformation and cyberattacks, for example in Lithuania, alongside the National Cyber Security Center in Kaunas, the volunteering group named ‘Elves’ also handles with Russian online information war (Coolican, 2021: 14). Thompson (2019) asserts that disinformation campaigns have an important role in Russian efforts to weaken the Western states, and recommends “coordination between governments, commercial technology companies and the news industry and social media platforms to identify and address information” for an effective counter reaction to Russian disinformation to combat with its new technics and new target countries like the

Baltic states. Bankauskaite et al (2022) points out that the Crimean Annexation was a milestone for Lithuania and the 'Gerasimov Doctrine' and hybrid warfare became the key jargons for explaining Russian military approach and Lithuania's reaction.

Apart from the Baltic states' individual counter measuring activities against the disinformation activities by Russia, these countries also depend on EU's East StratCom Task Force that was created in 2015 to combat with Russian disinformation campaigns. The EU East StratCom Task Force "reports on and analyses disinformation trends, explains and exposes disinformation narratives, and raises awareness of the negative impact of disinformation that originates in pro-Kremlin sources and is disseminated in the Eastern neighborhood's information space and beyond" (European Union External Action).

Conclusion

Soft power strategies give special importance to diaspora. Diasporas are mostly used as a tool for foreign policies. Mostly these strategies include public diplomacy and cultural diplomacy activities focusing on culture, language, religion, and history to build up bridges to the hearts of other peoples, yet propaganda, intelligence gathering, hacking, and disinformation change the balance towards hard power usage and result in a transformation into a hybrid warfare. The compatriot policy of Russia was not actually a soft power one since the concept was created on 'protecting' the citizens from the beginning as a duty coming from the Constitution and federal laws. Nevertheless, Russia played the card of applying soft power well at the beginning of the 2000s while flirting with the West and the USA following the 9/11 on a mutual motto of 'global war on terrorism', but the Georgian War in 2008 and the Annexation of Crimea in 2014 were not so late to remind the main objective behind the activities of the compatriot policies, particularly in the Baltics. The EU accession and NATO membership of the Baltic countries in 2004 changed the game in the Baltic region and Russia getting more aggressive with Georgian and Ukrainian politics chose to shift from soft power policies to a hybrid warfare in the Baltics, especially after the Crimean Annexation and Ukrainian War in 2022.

This study fills the gap in the literature regarding this transformation of the compatriot policy as a soft power strategy into a hybrid warfare since the literature mostly focuses on how Russia has been using soft power strategies in the post-Soviet countries and the fading soft power of Russia. However, the recent developments in Europe before and after the Ukrainian War brought along significant changes in the Russian strategies in the Baltics. Russia has left softer politics of public and cultural diplomacy and recently has been applying hard power techniques even if not directly in a battle with the Baltic states. Further studies can focus on the countermeasures against the Russian hybrid warfare benefitting from the compatriot policies in the region and its future predictions regarding the Baltic states and the NATO. Since those 'privileged interests' of Russia as stated by Medvedev in the region might require waging wars on these small Baltic states without a military support coming from the NATO, where also gained importance with the risk of a possible usage of the 'Suwalki Gap' by Russia to reach out the Kaliningrad enclave during a future clash in the Baltics.

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